

THE NATURE AND CHARACTERISTICS OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Annotation: This paper aims to extend our understanding of what it means to be a language teacher by examining ways in which language teachers are seen to be different to teachers of other subjects. Language teachers’ distinctiveness was defined by over 200 practising and prospective language teachers from a range of contexts, and the analysis also included the opinions of specialists in mathematics, history, science and chemistry on the extent to which characteristics claimed to be distinctive of language teachers applied to these other subjects.

Key words: language, teachers, history, classroom

The findings of the study suggest that language teachers are seen to be distinctive in terms of the nature of the subject, the content of teaching, the teaching methodology, teacher–learner relationships, and contrasts between native and non-native speakers. The study also raises methodological and conceptual issues of relevance to further research into this area. Key amongst these are the need to define language teachers’ distinctive characteristics with reference to specific contexts rather than globally, the importance of comparisons between insider views on such distinctiveness and those from outside language teaching, and the value of comparative studies of actual classroom practices of language teaching and other subjects.

I Introduction This paper reports an exploratory study into the distinctive characteristics of language teachers, specifically of teachers of English as a foreign language. A basic assumption here is that it should be possible to distinguish teachers of different subjects from each other in ways which go beyond simple references to

their diverse subject matters. A second assumption is that this is a key issue for teacher educators; language teacher education presupposes an understanding of what specifically it means to be a language teacher, and therefore insight into the distinctive characteristics of language teachers is central to the work of language teacher educators. I will start by discussing the literature that informed the research I present here. A description of the principles and procedures involved in the conduct of the research follows, and the findings are then presented. The paper concludes with a discussion of key issues to emerge from this work and suggestions for continuing research into this topic. Two framing comments are necessary before proceeding. First, teachers of English as a foreign language are taken here to be individuals involved in supporting the learning of the English language by learners whose contact with this language in their own countries is limited largely to the classroom. Second, it may be helpful to point out from the outset that although the focus of this study is on the characteristics of language teachers, the findings suggest that these cannot be considered in isolation of the characteristics of language teaching. The paper, therefore, does ultimately explore both teachers and teaching.

1 Language teachers’ characteristics Two areas of literature informed the research I present here: (a) work on disciplinary characteristics and (b) studies of the good language teacher. I discuss each of these in turn below.

a Disciplinary characteristics: The study of the characteristics of academic disciplines is an established field of enquiry in psychology and education (e.g. Becher and Trowler, 2001; Biglan, 1973; Hativa and Marinovich, 1995). Most of this work has been conducted in university settings, and, as Neumann (2001) highlights in her review, there is evidence of a range of ways in which teaching practices at university level may vary across disciplines (e.g. ‘hard’ disciplines, such as physics and engineering, emphasize cognitive goals such as learning facts, while ‘soft areas’, such as humanities and education, focus more on general knowledge, character development and effective thinking skills). Work on disciplinary characteristics outside university settings has focused largely on learners rather than teachers (but see Langer, 1994). The same is

true in the field of language teaching (e.g. Mori, 1999), though one exception here is Hammadou and Bernhardt (1987: 305), who discuss what they call ‘the unique art of being a foreign language teacher’. Within a North American context, they argue that Being a foreign language teacher is in many ways unique within the profession of teaching. Becoming a foreign language teacher, too, is a different process from that which other future teachers experience. This reality is rooted in the subject matter of foreign language itself. In foreign language teaching, the content and the process for learning the content are the same. In other words, in foreign language teaching the medium is the message. (1987: 302) Five factors that distinguish the experience of foreign language (FL) teachers from that of teachers of other subjects are proposed by these authors. These factors are as follows: 1) The nature of the subject matter itself. FL teaching is the only subject where effective instruction requires the teacher to use a medium the students do not yet understand. 2) The interaction patterns necessary to provide instruction. Effective FL instruction requires interaction patterns such as group work which are desirable, but not necessary for effective instruction in other subjects. 3) The challenge for teachers of increasing their knowledge of the subject. Language teachers teach communication, not facts. In other subjects, teachers can increase their subject matter knowledge through books, but it is harder for FL teachers to maintain and increase their knowledge of the FL because doing so requires regular opportunities for them to engage in FL communication. 4) Isolation. FL teachers experience more than teachers of other subjects feelings of isolation resulting from the absence of colleagues teaching the same subject. 5) The need for outside support for learning the subject. For effective instruction, FL teachers must seek ways of providing extracurricular activities through which naturalistic learning environments can be created. Such activities are less of a necessity in other subjects. No empirical support is provided for the above claims, and I highlight them here not to argue for their validity but as an example (and a rare one it would seem) of the manner in which language teachers’ distinctive characteristics have been conceptualized. For the

same reason, the work of Grossman and Shulman (1994: 4), who comment specifically on the special nature of the subject matter of English, is also relevant here. They say it is less amenable to definition than others, quoting an earlier paper by Grossman (1993) to argue that As an inherently ambiguous subject, which is less hierarchically organized than is math and encompasses a variety of subdomains, English may offer teachers greater freedom within the confines of the classroom. As it would be difficult, if not impossible, for teachers to cover all of the territory encompassed by the subject of English, teachers may necessarily select the purposes and areas they plan to emphasize in their classrooms. The inherent complexity of the subject, with its separate domains and subcomponents, may also offer teachers greater autonomy in developing curriculum. (1994: 4) The two studies discussed above highlight a range of issues which may be relevant to understanding language teachers’ distinctiveness. Both suggest that the nature of the subject matter is a significant dimension to consider, while Hammadou and Bernhardt’s work indicates that language teachers’ may also be characterized by a distinctive pedagogy as well as by particular emotional or social concerns (i.e. isolation). b The good language teacher: While the work on disciplinary characteristics discussed above provides the main theoretical motivation for this study, research on the good language teacher is also relevant here in highlighting ways in which language teachers’ characteristics have been conceptualized. I will therefore comment briefly on this work. Girard (1977), for example, presented a list based on the views of language learners and which included items such as: makes his course interesting, teaches good pronunciation, explains clearly, speaks good English, shows the same interest in all the pupils, makes the pupils participate and shows great patience. Prodromou (1991) presented a much longer list of characteristics valued by learners; examples cited were friendly, gave good notes, played games, told jokes, did not push weak learners and was more like a comedian. Brosh (1996) identified the desirable characteristics of the effective language teacher as perceived by foreign language teachers and

students in Israel. The following five characteristics emerged overall as those felt to be most desirable by the participants in this study:

- knowledge and command of the target language;
- ability to organize, explain and clarify, as well as to arouse and sustain interest and motivation among students;
- fairness to students by showing neither favouritism nor prejudice;
- availability to students. It should be noted that the majority of items appearing

here reflect the results of research into the characteristics of good teachers more generally (see, for example, studies by Hay McBer, 2000; Walls et al., 2002). This is not particularly surprising as language teachers are after all teachers and will therefore embody characteristics of the teaching profession more generally. Also, the purpose of these studies was not so much to define what was distinctive about language teachers but to identify what learners and teachers felt were effective or desirable characteristics. None the less, this research does highlight a range of issues which may be relevant to the study of language teachers’ distinctive characteristics. Particularly salient here are references to teachers’ personal characteristics; additionally, there are many references to characteristics related to teachers’ knowledge, skills and attitudes towards the learners. This introduction, then, has located the present study within an existing broader area of inquiry into disciplinary characteristics. It has also indicated that little work of this kind, focusing specifically on language teachers, has been conducted. The work that has been done in this respect, together with that into the good language teacher, does, however, demonstrate that the notion of language teachers’ characteristics is complex and multi-dimensional, and a range of different perspectives from which language teachers’ distinctiveness might be defined was identified. The research described in this paper aimed to uncover which particular dimensions would be salient when practising and prospective language teachers themselves were asked to describe the ways in which they believed language teachers to be distinctive and when the perspectives of specialists in other subjects were also considered. Language teachers

is used throughout this paper to refer to teachers of English as a foreign language, as defined earlier.

II Method In terms of underlying methodological principles, the research presented here reflects a preference for interpretive modes of inquiry (see, for example, Ernest, 1994 for a discussion) and a belief in the value of individuals’ perspectives on the phenomenon under study (examining what teachers think and believe has in recent years furthered our understanding of language teaching – see, for example, Borg, 2003). The research design adopted was flexible, as opposed to fixed (Robson, 2002). A fundamental difference between these two approaches lies in the extent to which design decisions can evolve as the study proceeds, with the flexible option of ‘allowing for and anticipating changes in strategies, procedures, ways of generating data [which are] responsive to the circumstances of the particular study’ (Schwandt, 1997: 34). Given the exploratory nature of this study and the lack of established empirical and methodological frameworks for work of this kind, this design was appropriate here, allowing decisions about data collection at each stage of the study to be informed by and responsive to the findings emerging from preceding phases. A flexible design does, of course, still need to be implemented in a principled manner and, as intended in the account that follows, reported in such a way that the reasoning behind the decisions at each stage of the process is made explicit.

1 Key concepts The key concept in this study was the notion of language teachers’ characteristics. As illustrated earlier, this is a broad concept which can be defined from a number of perspectives highlighted in existing research on language teaching. Teachers’ characteristics can thus, for example, be defined in terms of personal qualities, pedagogical skills, classroom practices, subject matter and psychological constructs such as knowledge and attitudes. No a priori decisions were made here about which of these particular perspectives to focus on. The concept of teachers’ characteristics was thus operationalized broadly as respondents’ reported perceptions of the ways in which language teachers were different to teachers of other subjects. Such an inclusive notion of this key concept is justified given that

one central goal of the study was to obtain insight into respondents’ perspectives on the distinctive characteristics of language teachers. 2 Research questions The work on disciplinary characteristics, which was discussed earlier, suggested one overall research question for this study: in what ways are perceived to be distinctive – i.e. different to teachers of other subjects? In this exploratory study, then, my goal was to examine this research question, to deepen my understanding of concepts and issues relevant to it, and to develop insights for subsequent research on it. Furthermore, as Maxwell (1996: 49) argues, in interpretive work, ‘specific questions are generally the result of an interactive design process, rather than being the starting point for that process’. Thus the overall question was broken down into the following more specific ones as the work proceeded and each set of data was analysed:

- Which particular dimensions of teachers’ characteristics are salient in the distinctiveness of language teachers as reported by the respondents?
- Do perceptions of distinctiveness seem related in any way to respondents’ backgrounds, such as amount of teaching experience or educational context?
- To what extent do specialists outside language teaching feel that the distinctive characteristics of language teachers perceived by language teachers also apply to teachers in the specialist areas?

3 Data collection and analysis Data were collected in a range of contexts, with a variety of individuals and using different procedures. Such variety is acknowledged as a factor contributing to the validity of research having a qualitative orientation (see, for example, the discussion of triangulation in Maxwell, 1996). Five different groups of participants, described below, contributed to this study. The selection of groups was purposive (Patton, 1990: 169–86), defined as a strategy in which participants are included in a study on the basis of their ability, as judged by the researcher, to provide information relevant to the central purposes of the research. Thus four of the five groups were chosen on the basis that they had experience of the phenomenon under study here, i.e. experience of teaching and/or learning English as a foreign language. To obtain a range of perspectives, two groups were experienced teachers while two were in training. Additionally, a fifth group of

subject specialists from outside language teaching was included to provide an interdisciplinary perspective on the topic being examined. What follows is a description of the five groups of participants in turn together with the data collection and analysis procedures used with each.

a Teachers on a postgraduate course in TESOL: The first group of respondents functioned as pilot group which enabled me to assess whether the topic was one worth pursuing and, assuming it was, to generate some initial ideas to build on in subsequent phases of data collection. This group consisted of 20 teachers on a postgraduate course in TESOL studying at the author’s university. These were all practising teachers of English as a foreign language from a range of contexts around the world. They had 3–14 years of experience, were predominantly non-native speakers of English, and were registered on an MA course in TESOL. These teachers attended periodic seminars on issues of relevance to language teaching, and one of these seminars was run by myself on the theme of ‘What makes language teachers different?’ During the seminar, the participants discussed this question, first in groups then in plenary. My role in the discussion was to provide the background to the topic, to set up and facilitate the small-group and plenary discussions, and to make written notes of the points emerging during the latter. Following the session, I used these notes to produce a list of eight distinctive characteristics of language teachers. This initial analysis suggested that the topic was one worth exploring further.

b Language teacher conference delegates: The second group of participants consisted of 29 delegates at a workshop entitled ‘What makes language teachers different?’, which I ran at an international language teachers’ conference in the UK. This group consisted mainly of experienced teachers of English as a foreign language, working in a variety of settings in the UK and Europe. During the workshop, I presented to the participants the list of characteristics emerging from my work with the postgraduate teachers and asked them to critique and to add to this list. Participants engaged in oral discussion, recorded their observations in writing and handed their written comments in at the end of the session. Each set of written comments was transferred verbatim to two grids. The

first contained respondents’ comments on the original list and was divided into eight sections, one for each of the eight original items. This grid provided information about the volume of comments on each original item as well as about the opinions given by respondents on these items. The second grid contained a list of 25 additional distinctive characteristics of language teachers suggested by the respondents. A thematic analysis of this diverse list suggested broad categories, such as ‘subject matter’ and ‘methodology’, into which the characteristics could be organized. As a result of the analysis of the data from these respondents, I drew up a revised, extended list of 18 distinctive characteristics of language teachers. c Subject specialists: The inclusion of the subject specialists in the study was prompted by the analysis of the first two sets of data, which, as illustrated below, contained a number of characteristics which prima facie could not be justifiably claimed to be unique to language teachers. To consider the value of an interdisciplinary perspective here, then, four subject specialist teacher educators at the author’s university, one each in science, chemistry, mathematics and history, were asked to comment on the extent to which they felt each of the items in the extended list of characteristics might also apply to their own fields. Each specialist was sent the list of characteristics by e-mail, with instructions, and their responses were e-mailed back. The data generated by this group did suggest that an interdisciplinary perspective can be a useful element in continuing studies of language teachers’ distinctiveness. The analysis of the data from this group is explained with the findings below. d Hungarian pre-service teachers of English: The first two groups of language teachers in the study were practising teachers from a range of different language teaching contexts. In addition, the perceptions of language teachers’ distinctiveness held by two, more homogenous, groups of prospective teachers were also elicited. The first group consisted of 151 Hungarian pre-service teachers of English. They responded in writing to the question ‘Do you think there are any differences between a language teacher and a teacher of any other subject? If YES, what differences are there?’ The responses to the second part of this question were

analysed qualitatively. This involved a process of tabulating, free coding and categorizing the written responses (for discussions of some principles of qualitative data analysis, see Miles and Huberman, 1994; Patton, 1990; Tesch, 1990). All written responses were first transferred in full and sequentially into a grid, and content analysis was then applied to this grid to code the responses according to the specific distinctive characteristics they referred to. The coded responses were subsequently sorted into broader categories.

e Slovene undergraduates in English: The final group of participants in this study consisted of 24 Slovene undergraduate students studying English, who would all have the option, later in their programme, of qualifying as teachers of English. At the time of the study, these students were studying English content (language and literature) and had no experience of teaching themselves. The data collected from these participants consisted of essays of 150–300 words on the topic ‘What makes language teachers different?’ Students were regularly asked to complete writing assignments on their course and this data collection technique was thus felt to be one they would be familiar with. Data were analysed qualitatively, using a similar procedure to that adopted with the Hungarian responses. The main difference here was that each respondent wrote extensively on the topic and thus larger chunks of text needed to be extracted, tabulated, coded and categorized.

III Findings I will now present the findings that emerged from the analysis of the data collected at each stage outlined above. The generalization of these findings beyond the groups studied is not a concern here; what is more important, both in this section and in the subsequent discussion, is understanding how language teachers’ distinctiveness is perceived by the respondents in this study and what these findings suggest – substantively, conceptually and methodologically – for continuing research into this topic.

1 Teachers on a postgraduate course in TESOL The discussion with postgraduate teachers yielded the following list of distinctive characteristics of language teachers and of their work: 1) Cognitively mature learners engage in conceptually undemanding activities. In language learning there is often a gap between the level of knowledge or skill the learner is being asked

to demonstrate, and the more general cognitive ability of the learner. 2) English language teaching methodology is more progressive than other subjects. The field of English language teaching is more advanced and innovative in its approach to teaching and learning. 3) Incorrect learner output in language teaching is more acceptable. Language teachers accept learners' errors more than teachers of other subjects. 4) Language teachers are compared to native speakers. The ability of non-native language teachers is often equated with their proficiency in the language relative to native speakers. 5) Language teaching is a political activity. Language teaching has a dimension of power, and control, inducting learners into ways of thinking and being which reflect those of the target culture. 6) Oral production plays a central role. More than in any other subject, speaking is fundamental to language teaching. 7) The subject and the medium for teaching it are one and the same. Unlike other subjects where there is a clear distinction between what is being learnt and how it is being learned, in language teaching content and process are one. 8) The subject matter of language teaching is harder to define. The content of language teaching is more complex and varied than that of other subjects. Several themes that recur throughout this study were introduced here. In particular, point 4 introduced the distinction between native and nonnative teachers of English, while points 7 and 8 related to the nature of the subject matter in language teaching. As this paper shows, one of the most commonly cited reasons for the uniqueness of language teachers is the subject matter: two aspects of this were highlighted here – the unity of content and medium, and the complexity and variety of the content – but others emerged from subsequent data sets. This first data set also highlighted the fact that in order to identify what was unique about language teachers, the postgraduate teachers also described what was distinctive about language teaching. This suggests that teachers are defined by the nature of their work and that articulating the distinctive features of the language teacher must also include reference to aspects of their work, such as methods, learners and learning processes, which may contribute to this distinctiveness. The blurring of the distinction between teachers and teaching is one

which recurs throughout the data, and reflects points made earlier about the many interrelated perspectives from which language teachers’ distinctiveness can be defined. 2 Conference delegates The conference delegates were presented with the list of eight statements above and asked both to critique it and to suggest additional distinctive characteristics of language teachers. a Critique of original list: The delegates were asked to comment only on those items they did not feel were distinctive characteristics of language teachers, and to explain their views. Of the eight statements, three in particular (1, 2 and 6) generated many responses. Brief comments on these follow. • Cognitively mature learners engage in conceptually undemanding activities. Several delegates suggested other subjects, such as crafts, technology and adult numeracy, where there might be a gap between the level of knowledge or skill the learner was being asked to demonstrate, and their more general cognitive ability. Others disagreed altogether with the assumption behind this statement, arguing that ‘language learning is never undemanding – it always involves conceptual demands’. • ELT methodology is more progressive than other subjects. This statement generated numerous responses from the delegates, many of which disputed the methodological distinctiveness of language teaching. ‘Why is language teaching more progressive than, for example, history teaching? I really think this is not true’, one delegate commented. Another wrote that ‘in Germany, religious studies in secondary school is more innovative than language teaching. I would borrow ideas from this subject for my language classes’. Another dismissed the claim to progressiveness altogether: ‘ELT is not progressive – a lot of half-baked ideas get put out into the profession and this may actually stultify progress’. None the less, there were also several comments supporting the view that there was something unique about language teaching methodology, though ‘progressive’ was not always seen as the ideal term to capture this uniqueness. • Oral production plays a central role. A number of problems were pointed out with this statement as a distinctive characteristic of language teachers’ work. For instance, it was pointed out that ‘in many ELT contexts oral production is not essential. For example, in Brazil,

reading in English is what matters’. This comment points to the role that context may play in the way teachers’ distinctiveness is viewed, an issue that will be returned to later. For the remaining items in the original list of eight, few or no disagreements were voiced. b Further characteristics: Conference delegates were also asked to suggest additional distinctive characteristics of language teachers, resulting in a list of 25 items. Some reflect those identified by the postgraduate teachers, such as the comparisons, often unfavourable, that non-native teachers endure in respect of native speakers. There were also in this list items that once again refer to the uniqueness of the subject matter of language teaching; it includes ‘holistic growth’, ‘skills development’, ‘inter-cultural skills, social skills, and autonomy’, and thus is seen to be broader than other subjects where the focus is limited to specific content. Beliefs about the special methodological diversity of language teaching reappeared here too. Additionally, distinctive characteristics of language teachers were suggested in relation to the especially practical outcomes of their work, the low status of the subject, the wider range of knowledge required by teachers, and the fact that foreign language learners already know their mother tongue. The wide range of qualifications for and routes into English language teaching were also mentioned here as a distinctive characteristic of this field. One final point to make about this list relates to the sheer range of issues it covered. This was perhaps a reflection of the heterogeneity of this group, in particular diverse the range of contexts in which the respondents worked as language teachers. 3 Subject specialists On the basis of the analysis of data from the two groups of participants reported on above, I drew up an extended list of 18 statements about the distinctive characteristics of language teachers. Included in this list were Simon Borg 15 items generally accepted by the two previous groups as distinctive of language teachers (e.g. the unity of content and medium) and items that, despite some disagreement, reflected commonly held views about language teaching (e.g. regarding the acceptability of errors). To provide an interdisciplinary perspective on the phenomenon under study, these statements were submitted to four specialists in science, chemistry, mathematics and history. The

specialists were asked to comment on the extent to which they felt each of these characteristics applied to teachers of their respective subjects. Responses to each item provided by the subject specialists were coded according to whether they indicated that the phenomenon described existed in their subject (Yes), had some parallels (Partly), or did not exist (No). These responses are presented in Table 1. According to the notation used here, ‘No’ answers indicate that a statement was felt by the specialists not to characterize the work of teachers in their subjects. The distinctiveness to language teachers of a characteristic, then, can be discerned according to the overall number of ‘No’ answers it received out of a maximum of four. Statements 5, 10 and 12 stand out here as in each case all four specialists felt there that similar phenomena did not exist in their subjects. The first of these relates to the distinction between non-native teachers and native speakers referred to earlier. The second refers to the fact the foreign language learners already know their first language; they will have prior experience of developing mother tongue linguistic proficiency, which may provide points of reference for the process of foreign language learning. The specialists could not see parallels in their own areas. The third statement all specialists felt did not apply to their subjects related to the expeditious routes through which a language teaching qualification could be obtained. A second group of items emerge here as being characteristics largely distinct to language teachers. These were items where three out of four specialists felt the phenomena described in the statements did not apply to their subjects. Statements 1, 6, 11, 14, 15, 16 and 17 constitute this group. In five of these it was the mathematics specialist who felt a characteristic did or might apply to his field; for the other two it was the history specialist who felt the characteristics applied to teachers in his subject. For example, for Statement 1, regarding the acceptability of errors, the mathematics specialist felt that incorrect output was acceptable in his subject.

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